

**THE EFFECTIVENESS IN DEVELOPMENT OF BLENDED LEARNING
BASED ON DISCORD MEDIA ON ELASTICITY MATERIALS IN SMA
NEGERI 1 TOMOHON**

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ABSTRACT

The learning model that can be combined in blended learning is Inquiry-based Learning with Flipped Classroom which can make it easier for teachers to design or design, and develop classroom learning by utilizing existing technology. The location used in this research is SMA Negeri 1 Tomohon. This research was conducted in the even semester of the 2021/2022 academic year. Based on the description above, the implementation of Blended Learning with the use of the Learning Management System is very in line with current conditions and is expected to have a good, efficient, practical, and interesting effect. The ADDIE model was developed by Dick and Carry.. The stages that must be carried out in research in the ADDIE model are as follows: Analysis, 2. Design, 3. Development, 4. Implementation, and 5. Evaluation. Discord-based blended learning learning design is effective because it meets the research hypothesis of effectiveness testing through student learning outcomes tests

Keywords: bended learning, discord media, elasticity

INTRODUCTION

Physics is one of the branches of science that underlies the concept of living in harmony with nature. As a science that studies natural phenomena, physics also provides good lessons for humans to live in harmony based on natural laws. So that the paradigm of learning physics is often associated with phenomena that occur around them.

The problems of learning physics that are currently being faced are influenced by several factors and sources of problems, including the substance of the curriculum material, learning models, facilities/facilities for supporting learning activities, as well as the presence of students and an environment that does not allow students to study offline. One of the factors that are often found are learning methods and models that are not suitable to be applied in learning, especially physics lessons at this time.

Blended Learning can be used as an alternative in implementing learning and digitizing education. Blended Learning is a learning facility that combines various modes of delivery, teaching models, and learning styles, introducing various choices of media for dialogue between the facilitator and the person being taught. Blended learning is also a combination of face-to-face teaching and online teaching, but more than that as an element of social interaction. Blended Learning according to Semler (2005) is combining the best aspects of online learning, structured face-to-face activities, and real-world practices. Online learning systems, classroom training, and work experience have their own major drawbacks. The blended learning approach uses the strengths of each against the weaknesses of the others.

The learning model that can be combined in blended learning is Inquiry-based Learning with

Flipped Classroom which can make it easier for teachers to design or design, and develop classroom learning by utilizing existing technology.

Blended Learning is a solution for teachers in improving the quality of education and learning effectiveness. It is hoped that there will be innovations in learning technology that are more effective and passed on to teachers so that the quality is better which has an impact on improving the quality and competitiveness of students, so there must be product or media development that can be used in learning, especially in exact sciences such as elasticity material in class XI physics learning.

Elasticity in physics is the tendency of solid materials to return to their original shape after being deformed. A solid object will deform when a force is applied to it. If the material is elastic, the object will return to its original shape and size when the force is removed.

The implementation of blended elasticity learning requires an application, namely the Learning Management System (LMS). Learning Management System (LMS) is an application or software used to manage online learning which includes several aspects, namely material, placement, management, and assessment (Mahnegar, 2012).

Currently, there are many applications that can be used as media or Learning Management System platforms for learning using the Blended Learning model. There are several types of applications that can be used in the learning process including Schoology, Learnboos, Edmodo, Moodle, and others.

As for the Discord application, a Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) application designed to create community. Discord has the main advantages, namely the freedom to manage a server, voice and video calls, text messages, media and files that can be used individually or in groups. In addition to communication, in the Discord application you can add a Server to collect users, as well as Bots / Artificial Intelligence (AI) which are useful in Entertainment and Education bases. Discord can even combine media files used in learning such as PPT, Video, PDF, etc.

Previously Discord was only known by gamers to communicate and even create a community in it so that it could connect many people in one place (server). In the implementation of LMS, Discord still lacks exposure among teachers. (Jagad Dewantara, 2020)

Based on the description above, the implementation of Blended Learning with the use of the Learning Management System is very in line with current conditions and is expected to have a good, efficient, practical, and interesting effect. Therefore, researchers feel compelled to conduct research on "Development of Discord-Based Learning Blended Learning in Elasticity Materials at SMA Negeri 1 Tomohon".

RESEARCH METHODS

A. Development Research Design

The research method used in this study refers to the Research and Development Model with the ADDIE model which consists of five stages, namely Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation because the research model and This development is more rational and more complete than other models according to product development steps.

The ADDIE model was developed by Dick and Carry (1996). The stages that must be carried out in research in the ADDIE model are as follows: Analysis, 2. Design, 3. Development, 4. Implementation, and 5. Evaluation

B. Research Development Procedure

In this section, the researcher presents the procedural steps taken in the study, following the ADDIE procedure.

1. Research and Information Collecting (Analyze)

At this stage the researcher conducts a preliminary study or exploratory study to examine,

investigate, and collect information. This step is done by coming to SMA Negeri 1 Tomohon.

a. School Selection

The location used in this research is SMA Negeri 1 Tomohon. This research was conducted in the even semester of the 2021/2022 academic year. This location is used as a place for conducting research with the following considerations:

- 1) Principals and teachers who are cooperative and open to receive developments in education, especially development that supports the learning process
- 2) The school is accredited A, so it can be assumed that the quality of learning in schools is also qualified.

b. Material Selection

The material that will be developed in this research is elasticity material in class XI MIPA. The selection of this material is based on several reasons, one of which is because the use of this material is closely related to the problems of everyday life.

c. Analysis

Analysis is done by first analyzing the state of teaching materials as the main information in learning and the availability of teaching materials that support the implementation of a lesson. At this stage, the teaching materials that need to be developed will be determined to help students learn.

The needs of analysis that will be carried out includes curriculum analysis and technology analysis which is considered to represent the importance of developing learning media in this study, as follows: curricullums' analysis applied in most schools is the 2013 curriculum. The subject matter that will be developed is physics as an important material that underlies students to know the science of science. For technology analysis, this learning is using "web based learning." Four aspects of learning using the website are considered to have met the category as learning media: First, Materials. Internet-based media material is in the form of software (software) that functions to find learning references and learning resources, and what will be used is the Discord application. Second, Tools. Internet-based media utilize hardware in the form of smartphones, PC computers as tools to process and obtain learning references that contain information related to learning materials. Third, techniques, or routine procedures used to use tools, applying techniques are carried out by discussion and self-presentation. Fourth, Environment. The location of students is very possible to do outdoors.

2. Material and Media Design and Development Phase/Preliminary Development Form of the Product (Design and Development)

The learning design is designed and made based on the previous needs analysis and adapts the material in physics learning. The steps are as follows:

a. Initial Preparation of Materials and Media

The media used, namely Discord, is an application that can be directly accessed, so it can be developed immediately.

The steps in material design are as follows:

b. Formulate KI and KD according to those used in school

c. Designing material in the form of Power Point and inputting some references on the discord server.

The steps in designing LMS-Discord are as follows:

a. Discord server creation

b. Content creation on Discord servers

Next, the researcher will make an assessment or validation instrument that will be given to media experts and material experts as validators. The materials and media designed were developed and revised in several ways, namely material and media expert tests, as well as implementation in small group trials and large group trials.

3. Product Revision

Make revisions based on the results of the evaluation, namely the improvement and refinement of the products made.

4. Preliminary Testing

Products that have been made must of course pass an initial evaluation, which is carried out by material experts and media experts, namely lecturers and school teachers. The initial trial can also be referred to as the initial product validation stage.

5. Field Testing (Implementation)

Conduct field trials. The experiment was conducted by researchers only in one school. The trial aims to determine the feasibility of the product that has been developed. From this field test, a test of student learning outcomes will be obtained, and determine the effectiveness of the student activity sheet.

6. Product Evaluation and Revision/Post Operational Product Revision and Evaluation (Evaluation)

After the application of the product in the real class, the researcher distributed a questionnaire/questionnaire to teachers and students with the aim of seeing the responses of teachers and students to the product that had been developed, so that the level of practicality could be known. The Post Operational Product Revision is intended to make revisions if the results obtained do not meet the criteria.

C. Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

The data collection instrument in this study followed the ADDIE model development procedure (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) whereas the focus is to compare the effectiveness between control group and experimental group.

1. Effectiveness

This stage is the implementation stage or the implementation of giving products/treatments to students, to determine the effectiveness or learning outcomes of students before being given treatment through questions in the early stages of Pre-test, and test of learning outcomes (Post-test). The data collection technique was in the form of statistical test of learning outcomes in the experimental class and the control class.

D. Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis techniques used in this study include:

a. Learning Effectiveness Analysis (Effective Criteria Test)

b. Test Statistics Independent Samples T-Test

The conditions that must be met before conducting the T-test are:

1) Samples must be Independent

Independent samples t-test uses two groups that are independent to each other, in this case the group control XI thus both groups are not entitled to each other.

2) Normality Test through Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is carried out by making the following hypotheses:

Ho: data is normally distributed, if sig. 2-tailed > a + 0.05

H_a : the data is not normally distributed, if sig. 2-tailed $< \alpha + 0.05$

3) Homogeneity Test

The formulation of the hypothesis is:

- H_0 : There is no difference in the average student learning outcomes between the experimental group and the control group
- H_a : there is a difference in the average student learning outcomes between the experimental group and the control group

The basis for decision making in the hypothesis is as follows:

- If the value of Sig. (2-tailed) > 0.05 then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.
- If the value of Sig. (2-tailed) < 0.05 then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

The decision making is based on the comparison of the value of t_{count} with t_{table} in the independent samples t-test, namely:

- If the value of $t_{count} < t_{table}$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.
- If the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is rejected.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Description of Research Results

1. Effectiveness

The implementation phase is carried out to see the effectiveness of learning (learning outcomes). The results of the development of Blended Learning learning were implemented in a real class (field test) to 30 experimental class students, and to see the comparison/effectiveness of the resulting product, 30 control class students were taken as comparisons. Thus to analyze the comparison between control group and experimental group, Independent Sample T-Test is needed to compare the averages of two groups that are not related, so that it can be seen whether the two samples have the same average or not.

A) Output Interpretation, Group Statistics

It is known that the number of learning outcomes for both the control class and the experimental class is 30 each. The average value (mean) for the control class is 36.40, while the experimental class is 43.13. Thus, statistically descriptive, it can be concluded that there is a difference in the average learning outcomes of class students who use Discord-based blended learning products and those who do not use these products.

Table 6. Table of Statistics of Control Group and Experimental Group

Group Statistics					
	Kelas	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Hasil Belajar Siswa	Kelas Kontrol	30	36.40	5.367	.980
	Kelas Eksperimen	30	43.13	3.954	.722

B) Independent Samples Test

Based on the output above, it is known that the value of Sig. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances is $0.479 > 0.05$, it means that the data variance between the control group and the experimental group is homogeneous or the same (V. Wiratna, 2014)

So that the interpretation of the Independent Samples Test output table is guided by the values contained in the "Equal variances assumed" table. experimental group. The difference between these differences is -9,170 to -4,297 (95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Upper Lower)

Furthermore, the value of t_{count} is -5.532. The t_{count} value is negative because the average value of the learning outcomes of the first group (control group) is lower than the average value of

the learning outcomes of the second group (experimental group). Then the decision-making test of independent samples t-test through a comparison between the values of t_{count} and t_{table} can be continued, by changing the value of t_{count} to be positive, $t_{\text{count}} = 5.532$.

To find the value of t_{table} refer to the formula $t_{\text{table}} = t_{\alpha/2; (df)}$, is the level of significance, in this study is 0.05, while df is the degrees of freedom or degrees of freedom in this study, namely $60-2 = 58$. So that the t_{table} seen in the distribution table is 0.025;58, which is 2.00172, $t_{\text{table}} = 2.00172$.

Thus, $t_{\text{count}} 5.532 > t_{\text{table}} 2.00172$, so based on the basis of decision making through comparison of t_{count} and t_{table} values, it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is a difference in the average student learning outcomes between the control group and the experimental group, or in other words, the effectiveness of discord-based blended learning experiences differences and produces different learning outcomes.

IV. CONCLUSION

Discord-based blended learning design is effective because it meets the research of effectiveness testing through student learning outcomes between the control group and the experimental group.

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